

DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE COMPETENCE OF PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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ANNOTATION: If students' learning activities are not directed to creative thinking, if they do not become active individuals in the learning process, then their conscious mastery will never be achieved. It has been proven in practice that the initial training process is effective and gives good results if the following requirements are followed. Abilities are a set of mental and individual characteristics that allow acquiring important knowledge, skills and abilities for productive activity. Intellectual ability refers to the ability to use concepts and make logical generalizations. Creative imagination is the basis of the creative approach to intellectual and creative activities of high school students. The leading feature of the ability is creative imagination.

KEY WORDS: creative imagination, thinking, in the harmony of memory and perception, constructive-creative activity, educational process, education of students.

Today, the extraordinary conveniences and modern technologies created for mankind help young people to grow up with intellectual potential. Great strides in science and technology have led to unprecedented changes. Modern techniques and technologies have become the closest companion of our life today. Taking into account that the 21st century as the age of the information society covers the mind and thinking of the growing young generation in every way, it is clear that unprecedented scientific discoveries, huge technical possibilities, universal technologies, the globalization of information distribution is a powerful ideological influence tool, these processes are the happy future of man. Paying attention to serving for is becoming the most urgent tasks of today.

It is not wrong to say that the role of computer technology in young people's quick acceptance of news and information happening in our lives, effective use of it and bringing it to a new level is incomparable.

Today's globalization conditions require highly moral and all-round developed young people with a broad outlook and thinking ability in the society. The rapid growth of the information field, the rapid development of its automation methods led to the creation of a new generation of computers and the connection of personal life with it, the computerization of various areas of society, which, in turn, is extremely fast today. brought forth the theory of the growing information society.

Creativity is a combination of many qualities. The question of the components of human creativity is still open, although at the moment there are several hypotheses on this problem.

Creativity is divided into three main groups:

- 1) abilities related to motivation (interests and inclinations);
- 2) abilities related to temperament (emotionality);
- 3) mental abilities.

R. Sternberg states that the creative process is possible when there are three special intellectual abilities:

Synthetic ability to see problems from a new perspective and avoid the usual way of thinking;
 Analytical ability to assess whether ideas are worth further development;
 A practical-contextual ability to convince others of the importance of an idea.

If a person has highly developed analytical skills to the detriment of the other two, he is an excellent critic, but not a creator. Synthetic ability, not supported by analytical practice, gives rise to many new ideas, but not confirmed by research and useless. Without the other two, practical skills can lead to brilliantly expressed but "bad" ideas. Creativity requires thinking to be independent of stereotypes and external influences.

From Sternberg's point of view, creativity means the ability to take reasonable risks, the willingness to overcome obstacles, internal motivation, tolerance for uncertainty (tolerance), resistance to the opinions of others.

A well-known local researcher of the problem of creativity A.N. Based on the biographies of famous scientists, inventors, artists and musicians, Luke emphasizes the following creative abilities:

- 1) the ability to see the problem where others do not;
- 2) the ability to turn off mental operations, replace several concepts with one, and use signs that have more and more capacity in terms of information;
- 3) the ability to use the skills acquired in solving one problem in solving another problem;
- 4) the ability to perceive reality as a whole, without dividing it into parts;
- 5) the ability to easily connect distant concepts;
- 6) the ability of memory to produce the necessary information at the right time;
- 7) flexibility of thinking;
- 8) the ability to choose one of the alternatives to solve the problem before examining it;
- 9) the possibility of introducing newly perceived information into the existing knowledge system;
- 10) to be able to see things as they are, to be able to distinguish what is observed from what is brought by interpreting;
- 11) ease of creating ideas;
- 12) creative imagination;
- 13) the ability to clarify details, improve the original idea.

Candidates of psychology V.T. Kudryavtsev and V. Sinelnikov, based on a wide historical and cultural material (history of philosophy, social sciences, art, specific fields of practice), identified the following universal creative abilities formed in the process.

- 1) realism of imagination - a figurative understanding of some important, general trend or pattern of development of an integral object before a person has a clear idea about it and includes it in a system of strict logical categories;
 - 2) the ability to see the whole before the parts;
 - 3) the suprasituational-transformative nature of creative solutions, the ability to independently create an alternative rather than just a choice in solving a problem;
- Another quality that forms creative thinking is consistency, that is, the ability to see an object or phenomenon as a whole system, to perceive any object, any problem in a comprehensive manner, in various connections; the ability to see the unity of interconnections in the laws of events and development. The development of these qualities makes thinking flexible, original and effective.

A number of scientists are based on the connection of creative thinking with associations.

S. Mednik stated that the more creative the thinking, the longer the ideas between which associations appear, the more they should meet the requirements of the task and be distinguished by their usefulness. Ways of creative solutions based on associations: intuition, finding similarities between individual elements (ideas) and mediation of some ideas by others.

Abu Ali ibn Sina also paid special attention to this issue in his writings and was a supporter of teaching children together as a team rather than individually. Ibn Sina directed the students to study together. Such cooperative teaching helps to strengthen their desire to learn, develop each child's desire to compete with each other, and realize their existing talents. All this creates a basis for ensuring children's good reading and creative thinking.

If the students' learning activity is not directed to creative thinking, if they do not become an active person in the educational process, then their conscious mastery will never be achieved. It has been proven in practice that the initial training process is effective and gives good results if the following requirements are followed:

students are open to learning and actively engage in relationships and cooperation with other participants in the educational process;

they will have the opportunity to analyze their work and realize their personal potential;

ular yaqin vaqt ichida o'z hayotida va professional faoliyatida duch kelishi muqarrar bo'lgan vaziyatga amaliy jihatdan tayyorlanib olishlari mumkin;

o'zlariga ishonishlari, o'zlarini ifodalashga qo'rqmasliklari, xatoga yo'l qo'yishlari mumkin, qachonki ular buning uchun muhokama qilinmasalar va salbiy baholanmasalar.

Qobiliyatlar ruhiy-individual xususiyatlar majmui hisoblanib, mahsuldor faoliyat uchun muhim bilim, ko'nikma va malakalarni egallash imkonini beradi.

Intellektual qobiliyat tushunchalardan foydalana bilish, mantiqiy umumlashma mulohaza yuritish mahoratini anglatadi. Yuqori sinf o'quvchilarining intellektual-ijodiy faoliyatga kreativ yondashuvining negizini ijodiy tasavvur tashkil etadi. Qobiliyatning yetakchi xususiyati ijodiy tasavvur qilishdir.

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